

DEVELOPMENT OF PROTECTIVE STRUCTURES OF THE RAILWAY
TRACK FROM ROCKFALL

Mekhmonov Mashkurbek Khusen o'g'li,
Doctor of Philosophy in Technical Sciences (PhD), docent Tashkent State
Transport University

m.mehmonov90@mail.ru

Khamidov Maksudjon Kamolovich
Assistent Tashkent State Transport University

xamidov.m.k.0990@mail.ru

Makhamadjonov Shukhratjon Shavkat o'g'li
Assistent Tashkent State Transport University

shuhratshavkatovich0204@gmail.com

Abstrakt: The article presents the development of the design of mobile protective structures depending on the trajectory of stones in order to protect the railway track from rockfall.

Keywords: Complex condition, roadbed, railway, trajectory, rocks.

INTRODUCTION

Today, rail transport is becoming an important mode of transport of national transport networks with important advantages, such as a large volume of traffic, reducing environmental pollution, improving passenger safety and comfort compared to other modes of transport [1].

When an earthquake occurs and the speed of traffic increases, longitudinal, transverse, and vertical vibrations are created on the roadbed [2].

Ensuring the safety of the railway track in difficult conditions is one of the urgent problems. To ensure the safe and reliable operation of railways, it is

necessary to increase the radii of vertical and horizontal curved lines and straight sections of track.

Analysis of the actual data on the survey of the consequences of destructive earthquakes shows that the intensity of the earthquake depends on the engineering-geological, hydrogeological and geomorphological structure of the area [3].

The proposed mobile fencing structures should have the following properties:

1. Be cheaper compared to existing ones.
2. To be able to increase power at an inexpensive cost due to the changing situation on the road.
3. The technology of operation and transfer of these structures should be technologically simple with the least amount of manual labor.

To ensure the high-speed movement of railways, the radii of vertical and horizontal curves increase, which often leads to a change in the location of the roadbed. Shifting the location of the roadbed leads to removal or convergence with protective engineering structures. They are most often massive retaining walls or enclosing walls that cannot perform their functions under the changed situations of the road location.

While ensuring the safety of railways running along the mountain, the protection of railway structures from rockfall remains the main task. One of the main goals should be the development of protective structures against rockfall and the choice of an acceptable option from an economic point of view. The geometric dimensions and shape of rockfall defenses primarily depend on the trajectory of the falling stone, below we will consider the following cases.

Rockfall refers to gravitational geological processes, which means the processes of change under the influence of gravity to the earth's surface. The process of falling rocks is one of the types of slope processes [4].

MAIN PART

Sliding is a trajectory motion with acceleration parallel to the surface of the slopes. In this movement, the rotation of the stone is not taken into account (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Stone sliding down the slope

Rotation is the movement of rocks with acceleration parallel to the slope surface, taking into account their rotational motion (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The rotational movement of the stone on the slope

A rock jump is one type of rock movement modeled as the interaction of the slope surface and the rock, occurring with a gradual deceleration of normal and tangential interaction forces (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The trajectory of the movement of the stone in leaps

The free fall of a stone is a movement with acceleration along a vertical trajectory without acting with a slope (Fig. 4) [5].

Fig. 4. The trajectory of free fall of rocks

Protective structures are developed depending on the trajectory of the above rocks. The rockfall of the roadbed and the upper structure of the railway track affects not only the safety and schedule of movement, but as a result, various deformations occur in the roadbed (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Rockfall of the railway track

The height of the protective structure is set depending on the trajectory of the movement of the stone for the maintenance of the railway track from the rockfall. If this height needs to be changed over time, then it will be necessary to change the protective structure based on experimental and model studies [6].

Based on the results of calculations , it is possible to obtain the following output data:

- 1) the total energy of the impact of the debris on the protective structure;
- 2) rebound height;
- 3) translational kinetic energy of the fragment;
- 4) rotational kinetic energy of the fragment;
- 5) translational velocity of the wreck;
- 6) angular velocity of the wreck;
- 7) moment of inertia of the wreck;
- 8) the moment of the fragment's momentum.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of mobile structures recommended by us will save operating costs (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Reinforcing layer with pile driving

1-reinforced concrete piles, 2-reinforcement with stone and rubble, 3-railway track.

When operating mobile protective structures, it is possible to change the parameters over time, which will allow you to restore the deformable part with less expense [7].

Inexpensive, but quite effective method of protecting the roadbed, are “hedgehog” fortifications also with a sketch of stone and rubble (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. “Hedgehog” fortifications with a sketch of a stone.

1- reinforced concrete “hedgehogs”, 2- reinforcement with stone and rubble, 3- railroad track, 4-pit for collecting stones [7]

CONCLUSION

1. The developed mobile protective structure for the maintenance of railways passing in difficult conditions from rockfall was created on the basis of resource-saving technologies.

2. A constructive solution of a mobile protective structure is given, which allows moving from an inactive site to an active one at a lower cost.

3. The existence of the possibility of changing the physical properties of mobile protective structures depending on the change in the trajectory of stones falling on the railway is substantiated.

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